

The Opisthobranch Molluscs from Porto Santo Island (Madeira Archipelago, Northeastern Atlantic)¹

Moluscos Opistobranquios de la Isla de Porto Santo (Archipiélago de Madeira, Atlántico Nordeste)¹

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ABSTRACT

New data on the opisthobranch fauna from Porto Santo island (Madeira Archipelago) are presented. A list of the previously recorded sixteen species and their relatives references, together the first record of twelve additional species, is supplied.

RESUMEN

En este trabajo se presentan nuevos datos sobre la fauna de moluscos opistobranquios de la isla de Porto Santo (Archipiélago de Madeira). Se confecciona una lista de las dieciseis especies previamente citadas en esta isla, junto a sus correspondientes referencias, la cual se ve incrementada con otras doce especies adicionales citadas por primera vez en esta contribución.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Opisthobranchia, Porto Santo, Madeira, Portugal.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Opisthobranchia, Porto Santo, Madeira, Portugal.

INTRODUCTION

Among the islands of Madeira Archipelago, Porto Santo is one of the less known with respect to the opisthobranchs. Only seven papers are known to us referring the presence of 16 species of opisthobranchs in Porto Santo (WATSON, 1897; NOBRE, 1937; NORD-

SIECK, 1972; NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA, 1979; WIRTZ, 1994; FONSECA, GUERREIRO AND GIL, 1995; WIRTZ, 1999).

Porto Santo is the second largest island of Madeira archipelago and is situated 21 miles on the Northeast of Madeira island. It lies between 33° 07' N

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Figure 1. (A) Madeira archipelago and (B) Porto Santo Island with sampling localities. 1 Ilhéu de Ferro; 2: Porto de Abrigo; 3: Pedras Altas; 4: Ilhéu do Farol; 5: Ponta da Galé; 6: Porto dos Frades; 7: Pontinha.

Figura 1. (A) Archipiélago de Madeira y (B) Localidades de muestreo en la Isla de Porto Santo: 1: Ilhéu de Ferro; 2: Porto de Abrigo; 3: Pedras Altas; 4: Ilhéu do Farol; 5: Ponta da Galé; 6: Porto dos Frades; 7: Pontinha.

– 33° 00' N and 16° 25' W – 16° 17' W and has an approximate area of 41 Km² with a coastal line of 38 Km. It is surrounded by seven islets, three of them with considerable dimensions. The littoral of Porto Santo is quite different from that of Madeira, mostly due to the presence of calcareous rocks and a large sandy beach. Whether these features are responsible or not for any particular faunistic composition of Porto Santo's littoral ecosystems is not yet known, by lacking of available ecological information.

As part of the research Programme OpisthoMadeira, launched in 1994 by the Museu Municipal do Funchal (História Natural), several field sampling were carried on Porto Santo island, which results are reported here together with a compilation of the previous bibliographical records.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

During the period of 18 to 23 September 2000, opisthobranch molluscs were

collected in eight different localities in a total of ten sampling efforts, covering both the intertidal and the subtidal areas down to 20 meters depth. On the subtidal areas the specimens were collected by SCUBA diving, using a suction device and by manual collecting after direct observation. Substratum covered with seaweeds, sponges, bryozoans and hydrozoans colonies were particularly searched.

After sieving, the specimens were studied with stereomicroscopes, photographed, fixed in formalin 4% and preserved in ethanol 70%.

The specimens were kept in the collections of the Museu Municipal do Funchal (História Natural) (designated as MMF).

RESULTS

Fourteen species were collected and identified during the present Campaign (1 Cephalaspidea, 1 Anaspidea, 1 Saccoglossa, 2 Tyrodinoidea, 1 Pleurobranchoidea, and 8 Nudibranchia) and

Table I. Opisthobranch molluscs from Porto Santo island.

Tabla I. Moluscos Opistobranquios de la Isla de Porto Santo.

Cephalaspidea Fischer, 1863 (*sensu* MIKKELSEN, 1996)

<i>Chelidonura africana</i> Pruvot-Fol, 1953	Present account. Porto de Abrigo, 18th September 2000, one specimen with 3 mm in length. 22nd September 2000, one specimen (MMF31629) with 3mm in length, collected at night time under a floating jetty.
<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i> (Pennant, 1767)	NORDSIECK (1972: 15), NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 170)
<i>Pyrunculus spretus</i> (Watson, 1897)	WATSON (1897: 234), NOBRE (1937: 15)
<i>Philine monterosatoi</i> (Vayssière, 1885)	NORDSIECK (1972: 22 as <i>Philingwynia monterosati</i>), NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 171)
<i>Philine desmotis</i> Watson, 1897	WATSON (1897: 236), NOBRE (1937: 17) and NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 172)
<i>Retusa truncatula</i> (Bruguière, 1792)	WATSON (1997: 326 as <i>Utriculo truncatulus</i>), NORDSIECK (1972: 34 as <i>Retusa mariei</i>), NOBRE (1937: 14 as <i>Tornatina truncatula</i>)
<i>Retusa mamillata</i> (Brusina, 1865)	NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 177 as <i>Retusa (Mamilloretusa) mamillata</i>)
<i>Retusa leptoleinema</i> (Brusina, 1865)	NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 176 as <i>Retusa leptoleynema</i>)
<i>Retusa tornata</i> (Watson, 1883)	NORDSIECK (1972: 36 as <i>Semiretusa tornata</i>), NORDSIECK AND GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979: 177 as <i>Semiretusa tornata</i>)
<i>Scaphander (W.) diaphana</i> Aradas and Maggiore, 1839	WATSON (1897: 315), NOBRE (1937: 14)

Anaspidea Fischer, 1883

<i>Aplysia parvula</i> Guilding in Mörch, 1863	Present account. Porto de Abrigo, 20th September 2000, one specimen (MMF31626) with 20 mm in length. 22nd September, three specimens (MMF31631) with 2,5, 3 and 4 mm in length, collected during night time under a floating jetty.
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Sacoglossa Ihering, 1876

<i>Ascobulla fragilis</i> (Jeffreys, 1856)	WATSON (1897: 284) and NOBRE (1937: 16)
<i>Elysia flava</i> Verril, 1901	Present account. Pontinha, 22nd September 2000, one specimen (MMF31636) with 9 mm in length, collected under a stone at 10 m depth.

Pleurobranchoidea Ferussac, 1822

<i>Berthellina edwardsi</i> (Vayssière, 1896)	Present account. Ilhéu de Ferro (Southeast shore), 19th September, one specimen (MMF31637) with 13 mm in length, collected under a stone at 10 m depth.
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Tylodinoidea Gray, 1847

<i>Tylodina perversa</i> (Gmelin in L., 1791)	WIRTZ (1999: 6), Present account. Ilhéu de Ferro (Southeast shore), 19th September 2000, one specimen with 4 mm of shell length, collected near the sponge <i>Aplysina aerophoba</i> at 10 m depth. Pedras Altas, 20th September 2000, two specimens with 5 mm of shell length, collected near the sponge <i>Aplysina aerophoba</i> at 3 m depth. Ilhéu do Farol (Southeast shore), 21st September 2000, one specimen with 7 mm in length.
<i>Umbraculum umbraculum</i> (Lightfoot, 1796)	Present account. Pontinha, 22nd September 2000, one specimen (MMF31634) with 50 mm of shell length, collected crawling on a wall at 10 m depth.

Table I. Continuation.

Tabla I. Continuación.

Nudibranchia Blainville, 1814

<i>Aegires sublaevis</i> Odhner, 1931	Present account. Porto dos Frades, 21st September 2000, one specimen (MMF31624) with 3,5 mm in length, collected bellow algae between 0 and 1 m depth.
<i>Aldisa smaragdina</i> Ortea, Pérez and Llera, 1982	Present account. Ilhéu de Ferro (Southeast shore), 19th September 2000, five specimens (MMF31641) with 10, 12, 14, 16 and 20 mm in length, under stones covered by a red sponge at approximately 10 m depth. Pedras Altas, 20th September 2000, one specimen with 23 mm in length, collected at 3 m depth, under a stone with red sponges.
<i>Chromodoris purpurea</i> (Laurillard, 1831)	Present account. Porto de Abrigo, 20th September 2000, one specimen (MMF31632) with 7 mm in length, collected under a stone at 4 m depth. Porto de Abrigo (out part of the west harbour protection near the beach), 23rd September 2000, one specimen (MMF3164) with 10 mm in length, collected under a stone between 4 to 5 m depth.
<i>Discodoris atromaculata</i> (Bergh, 1884)	WIRTZ (1994: 169; 1999: 7)
<i>Discodoris confusa</i> Ballesteros, Llera and Ortea, 1984	WIRTZ (1999: 8), Present account. Ponta da Galé, 18th September 2000, one specimen with 40 mm in length, collected under a stone at 6 meters depth.
<i>Hypselodoris bilineata</i> (Pruvot-Fol, 1953)	WIRTZ (1999: 7)
<i>Hypselodoris picta</i> (d'Orbigny, 1839)	Present account. Ilhéu de Ferro (Southeast shore), 19th September 2000, one specimen (MMF31623) with 50 mm in length, collected under a stone at 9 m depth
<i>Tambja ceutae</i> García-Gómez and Ortea, 1988	Present account. Porto de Abrigo, 22nd September 2000, five specimens (MMF31627) with 4, 16, 20, 26 and 27 mm in length, collected at night time under a floating jetty on colonies of the bryozoan <i>Bugula dentata</i> .
<i>Taringa</i> cf. <i>fanabensis</i> Ortea and Martínez, 1992	WIRTZ (1999: 9)
<i>Platydoris argo</i> (Linné, 1767)	Present account. Ilhéu de Ferro (Southeast shore), 19th September 2000, two specimens (MMF31625) with 18 and 28 mm length, collected under stones at about 10 m depth. Pontinha, 22nd September 2000, two specimens (MMF31642) with 10 and 12 mm in length, collected under stones at about 10 m depth.
<i>Plocamopherus maderae</i> (Lowe, 1842)	Present account. Pontinha, 22nd September 2000, one specimen (MMF31622) with 20 mm in length, collected under a stone at 10 m depth.

(Right page) Figure 2. A: *Chelidonura africana* (10 mm; specimen collected at Porto Santo, 24th June 1999); B: *Aplysia parvula* (20 mm); C: *Tylodina perversa* (7 mm); D: *Umbraculum umbraculum* (50 mm of shell length); E: *Elysia flava* (9 mm); F: *Berthellina edwardsi* (13 mm); G: *Aegires sublaevis* (7 mm; the illustrated specimen is from the southern coast of Madeira Island); H: *Tambja ceutae* (20 mm).

(Página derecha) Figura 2. A: *Chelidonura africana* (10 mm; ejemplar capturado en Porto Santo el 24 Junio 1999); B: *Aplysia parvula* (20 mm); C: *Tylodina perversa* (7 mm); D: *Umbraculum umbraculum* (50 mm de longitud de la concha); E: *Elysia flava* (9 mm); F: *Berthellina edwardsi* (13 mm); G: *Aegires sublaevis* (7 mm; el ejemplar ilustrado proviene de la costa sur de la Isla de Madeira); H: *Tambja ceutae* (20 mm).

twelve of them are new records for Porto Santo island. Table I shows this news records and all the explicit historical and recently references for opisthobranch molluscs on Porto Santo island.

DISCUSSION

Despite the new records for Porto Santo, it must be pointed out that all the species were already known for Madeira Island. Our record of *Elysia flava* is a confirmation of the hypothetical occurrence of this species in the archipelago since Ortea, Moro and Espinosa (1997) have quoted this sacoglossan species for Madeira without providing any information about the location of those specimens. However, the geographical distribution given by Ortea, Moro, Bacallado and Espinosa (1998) for this species does not include Madeira.

Four apparently undescribed species, two of them belonging to the cephalaspidean genus *Runcina* and the remaining to the nudibranch genera *Geitodoris* and *Cratena*, were also collected and are currently under study.

Taking in account the present results (excluding the unidentified species) and the bibliographical data, we can say that the known opisthobranch fauna in Porto Santo island comprises a total of 28 species, 10 belonging to the Cephalaspidea, 1 to the Anaspidea, 2 to the Sacoglossa, 2 to the Tylodinoidea, 1 to the Pleurobranchoidea and 12 to the Nudibranchia.

Some remarks can be commented taking into consideration the geographic distribution of the species collected in Porto Santo Island. Most of the species (65.2%) are considered NE Atlantic Mediterranean species. About half of these (34 % of the total) are restricted

mainly to the Lusitanic + Mauritanic + Mediterranean area, being the temperate character (Mauritanic + Mediterranean) represented by the 17.4% of the total.

Those opisthobranch species only collected in the central Macaronesian archipelagos (Madeira islands and Canary islands) are here considered endemic of this area, and reach the 13% of the total (*Discodoris confusa*, *Pyrrunculus spretus* and *Philine desmotis*).

The presence of widely distributed species (circutropical, 8.7%; amphiatlantic, 4.4%), as well as, temperate or subtropical NE Atlantic species is not very significant (8.7%).

In conclusion, Porto Santo possesses an intermediate position between the European and African faunae. The South European and North African species are the most important components, being moderately low the participation of widely distributed species and central Macaronesian endemism. Additional data from future campaigns will surely improve our knowledge about the biogeographical relationships of the different Macaronesian archipelagos. Another interesting aspect is the evaluation of the importance of these islands as intermediate steps in the dispersion of temperate-subtropical species, as well as, the possible gradient of endemic species from Azores throughout Madeira and Canary up to Cape Verde, following the Eastern Gulf Stream branch and Canary current influence.

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(Right page) Figure 3. A: *Plocamopherus maderae* (20mm); B: *Chromodoris purpurea* (7mm); C: *Hypselodoris picta* (50mm); D: *Aldisa smaragdina* (12mm); E: *Discodoris confusa* (40mm); F: *Platydorhis argo* (28mm); G: *Aldisa smaragdina* (23mm).

(Página derecha) Figura 3. A: *Plocamopherus maderae* (20mm); B: *Chromodoris purpurea* (7mm); C: *Hypselodoris picta* (50mm); D: *Aldisa smaragdina* (12mm); E: *Discodoris confusa* (40mm); F: *Platydorhis argo* (28mm); G: *Aldisa smaragdina* (23mm).

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